

EFFECT OF RHIZOTORPHIN AND NH_4NO_3 ON THE FORMATION OF THE SOYBEAN SYMBIOTIC SYSTEM AND TOTAL NITROGEN FUND

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Annotation. It is shown that under the influence of rhizotorphin (*Rhizobium japonicum* 648b strain) and granular ammonium nitrate (NH_4NO_3), an effective symbiotic system is formed in the soils of the Kurdamir region that are not so free with nutrients, and due to this, its accumulation is increased due to the entry of additional nitrogen into the reproductive organs of the plant soybean (*Glicine hispida* L.) variety "Bravo". As a result, productivity increases significantly and the role of symbiotic nitrogen fixation in the formation of the total nitrogen pool of plants increases

Keywords: Soybean, rhizotorphin, granular NH_4NO_3 , symbiosis, total nitrogen

Аннотация. Показано, что в результате формирования эффективной симбиотической системы на бедных элементами питания почвах Курдамирского района под действием ризоторфина (*Rhizobium japonicum* 648b) и гранулированной аммиачной селитры (NH_4NO_3) происходит увеличение массы растений сои (*Glicine hispida* L.) сорта «Браво» за счет поступления дополнительного азота в их репродуктивные органы. В результате значительно повышается продуктивность и увеличивается роль симбиотической азотфиксации в формировании общего азотного фонда растений.

Ключевые слова: соя, ризоторфин, NH_4NO_3 , симбиоз, общий азот

The formation of an effective symbiotic system between legumes and symbiotic nitrogen fixers in desert conditions depends mainly on the genotype of the plant, its species composition, the activity of nitrogen-fixing microorganisms, the characteristics of the soil, its water and temperature conditions. Disturbance of the characteristics of any of these factors due to the influence of the environment or various agrotechnical measures leads to a change in the characteristics of biological nitrogen fixation. Therefore, the study of these factors to increase the share of biological nitrogen fixation in plant nitrogen nutrition in order to increase the productivity of legumes is considered one of the most relevant directions of our time [1,2,4].

Symbiosis between plants and microsymbionts is mainly regulated by the plants themselves, depending on soil and climatic conditions and the species of the plant [3, 5, 6].

The aim of the research was to study the effect of rhizotorphine and granular ammonium nitrate on the formation of the symbiotic system and morphological indicators of soybean plants grown in the Kurdamir region.

Object and method of the study. The soybean (*Glicine hispida* L.) variety "Bravo" was used as the object of the study. The experiments were conducted at the Karrar experimental station of the Institute of Botany, Kurdamir district. Some agrochemical indicators of the

experimental field were studied. The pH of the experimental field was determined to be -7.9; EC25 -0.67 ms/cm; carbonation (CaCO₃) -5.9%; humus 1.9%; nitrogen (N) -0.062%; phosphorus (P₂O₅) -182 ppm; potassium (K) -143 ppm. As we can see, the soils of the cultivated field are not very rich in nutrients and the humus content is much lower than normal. The seeds of the plant were soaked in rhizorhine (*Rhizobium japonicum* 648b strain) for 6 hours before sowing. Granular ammonium nitrate was applied to the field before sowing. Seeds of control plants were not inoculated with rhizobium bacteria and NH₄NO₃ was not used. The absolute dry weight of root nodules and the phytomass of the aboveground part of the plant were determined by weighing on a scale. Nitrogen fixation activity was determined by acetylene gas [7].

Results and discussion. Analysis of the obtained results showed that nodules were formed in the control variant. This indicates the absence of nodule bacteria specific for soybean in the soil in the field. Analysis of the literature shows that in the early stages of ontogenesis, dry matter and nitrogen accumulate relatively slowly in soybean compared to the fruit formation phase. Analysis of the results obtained from our experiments showed that along with the increase in the weight of nodules in a plant, their symbiotic activity also increases (Figures 1 and 2).

Granular ammonium nitrate has a positive effect on plant nitrogen nutrition only during the vegetative growth phase. At this stage, the absence of ammonium nitrate in the environment reduces the rate of dry matter and nitrogen accumulation. During the flowering phase, the plant's nitrogen requirement increases compared to the initial growth phase, and this requirement is mainly met by symbiotic nitrogen fixation (Figure 2). In this phase, symbiotic nitrogen fixation reaches its peak. The high activity of symbiotic nitrogen fixation occurs at the beginning of the reproductive phase due to the activity of the unit mass of rhizomes, and towards the end of ontogenesis due to the increase in the mass of rhizomes. In the fruit formation phase, the mass of rhizomes continues to increase, reaching 1.8 g per plant in plants treated with rhizotrophin, and 0.92 g in the variant of the combined use of rhizotrophin and ammonium (Figure 1).

The dry weight of the aboveground part of a plant in the control variant was 12.9 g, in the ammonium nitrate variant it was 14.6 g, in the rhizotrophin-treated plants it was 14.2 g, and in the rhizotrophin + ammonium nitrate variant it was 16.5 g. The weight of the fruits was 6.5, 7.2, 8.0, and 8.4 g, respectively (Figure 1).

At this time, approximately 52-54% of the total nitrogen entering the plant was formed due to nitrogen fixed by root nodules during the vegetation stage. Therefore, the intensive development of soybean fruit (bean) and the formation of seeds is not due to the reduction of

nitrogen accumulated in vegetative organs as a result of reuse in the early stages of development, but due to the nitrogen fixed as a result of the activity of root nodules at this stage. As a result, the amount of nitrogen absorbed symbiotically in the total nitrogen fund of soybean bean (95.6%) was higher than its amount in the total biomass (92.1%) (Figure 2).

Thus, in the soil and climatic conditions of the Kurdamir region, the use of rhizotorphin and granular ammonium nitrate has a positive effect on the formation of root nodules and a mixed type of nitrogen nutrition from the beginning of vegetation to the flowering phase, creating favorable conditions for the activity of the symbiotic system from the beginning of flowering to fruiting, becoming one of the main factors in the formation of the total nitrogen stock and grain yield.

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